

Analysing The Women’s Reservation Bill 2023: A Crack on the Glass Ceiling

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Abstract: Nearly three decades after its initiation, the Women's Reservation Bill, 2023, was passed by Parliament. This marks a historic step towards empowering women politically. The legislation reserves 33 per cent of seats for women in the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. This paper analyses the Women’s Reservation Bill, 2023, within its historical context, key clauses, and its significance in India’s patriarchal, multicultural society. It also examines challenges faced during implementation. The paper concludes that reserving seats for women to a certain extent can help create an egalitarian society by addressing gender issues and producing effective legislation that reflects the needs of Indian women.

Keywords: Parliament, Lok Sabha, State Assembly, Reservations, Women's Reservation Bill

1. INTRODUCTION

“We always held that when the men who have fought and struggled for their country’s freedom came to power, the rights and liberties of women too would be guaranteed....”

-Renuka Ray (freedom fighter, 1947)

Reserving seats for women in legislatures is a form of affirmative action designed to enhance their representation in law-making bodies. Thus, reservation policy allocates a specific number of seats to women candidates to combat centuries of gender-based oppression and promote greater gender equality in decision-making processes. The primary aim of women’s reservation is to create an inclusive political landscape by ensuring that women from diverse backgrounds have fair and equal opportunities to participate in governance. Globally, reservation policies have been implemented at different levels of government, including village councils, state assemblies, and national parliaments. The rationale behind gender-based reservations stems from the recognition of the structural barriers and discrimination that have historically restricted women's access to political power. By providing women with a defined and dedicated space in legislatures, policymakers can foster a more representative democracy that reflects the diversity of the population.¹

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The history of the women's reservation debate in India can be traced back to the movements for equal rights during the freedom struggle, debates in the Constituent Assembly, and Government policies aimed at enhancing women's roles in governance. During the pre-independence period, women contributed significantly to social reform movements, advocating for education and the abolition of child marriage. Leaders like Sarojini Naidu, Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay, and Annie Besant were pivotal in the push for recognizing women's equal rights (Desai & Tamsah, 2014)². Mahatma Gandhi leveraged the potential of women in his mass movements, such as the Salt Satyagraha and Quit India. However, there was still much to be accomplished on the political front. Despite limited opportunities, Begum Jahanara Shah became one of the few women elected to the Central Legislative Assembly in 1927.³ The Constituent Assembly, which was created indigenously, also failed to adequately highlight women's issues, as it had a significantly imbalanced sex ratio with only 15 women among its 389 members. Notably, women like Renuka Ray, Hansa Mehta, and Dakshayani Velayudhan opposed the idea of reservations during the Constituent Assembly debates. They believed such measures would compromise merit, undermine the principle of equal representation, and potentially deprive women of fair consideration for general seats. These women had full faith in the democratic process, believing it would ensure equal representation for both sexes.⁴

The Indian Constitution, adopted in 1950, upholds the principle of equality before the law (Article 14) and forbids gender-based discrimination (Article 15). The Directive Principles of State Policy obligate the state to promote gender equality and equality of opportunities for both men and women. The issue of reservation rose in 1931, when Sarojini Naidu and Begum Shah Nawaz submitted the official memorandum jointly issued on the status of women in the new Constitution by three women's bodies to the British Prime Minister.⁵ The report of the committee on the status of women in India, published in 1974, observed women's dismal status in politics, even after comprising the other half of the population. The committee was maiden in its approach to recommend gender-based quotas in political parties. The committee was vocal in its demand for women's reservation in municipal councils and panchayats.

The National Perspective Plan for Women, established in 1988, emphasized the need for reserving seats for women in legislative institutions. This plan anticipated the passage of the 73rd and 74th Amendment Acts to the Constitution, which formalized the reservation of one-third of seats, as well as one-third of the chairperson positions, at all levels of the Panchayati Raj Institutions and in urban local self-government for women. This reservation also included one-third of the seats allocated for women from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes.⁶

The Women's Reservation Bill (81st amendment bill) was introduced in the 11th Lok Sabha on 12 September 1996 by the Prime Minister Deve Gowda-led United Front government, providing one-third reservation for women in the Lok Sabha as well as the State Assemblies. But the essence of the bill was misunderstood by some political groups. Many other groups advocated quotas within quotas for women belonging to marginalised sections. Thus, lack of political will and the delaying tactics led to the lapse of the bill. The same scenario occurred again in 1998 with the 84th amendment and in 1999 with the 85th amendment. Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee tried his best to pass the bill, but he failed to get a consensus on the same.⁷

The National Policy for empowerment of Women, 2001 aimed at 'advancement, development and empowerment of women'. One of its policy prescriptions was gender parity in power-sharing, advocating full access and equal participation in legislatures, executive and judiciary. It recommended affirmative action for women in higher legislative bodies for a limited time frame.⁸

Amidst these policy recommendations and pressure from women's welfare groups, the UPA II, led by Prime Minister Manmohan Singh, passed the bill in the Rajya Sabha in 2010, but the legislation never saw the light of day in the Lok Sabha. The bill finally lapsed in 2014. Meanwhile, the Report on the Status of Women in India (2015) again reiterated the demand for reservation of seats for women in legislatures.

Finally, under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi's government (second term), in 2023, the Nari Shakti Vandana Adhiniyam bill was tabled in the Lok Sabha during a special session of Parliament on 19th September, 2023. The legislation was decisively passed by both houses of Parliament and enacted into law, marking a vital milestone in the pursuit of gender equality in independent India.⁹

2. NAARI SHAKTI VANDAN ADHINIYAM

The NAARI SHAKTI VANDAN ADHINIYAM was the first bill introduced in the new parliament building during India's Amrit Kaal. The bill aims to reserve seats for women in the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. It intends to allocate, as nearly as possible, one-third of all seats for women across the Lok Sabha, State Legislative Assemblies, and the Legislative Assembly of the National Capital Territory of Delhi. One-third of these seats will be reserved for women within the existing SC and ST quotas in the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies.¹⁰ The Women's Reservation Bill, 2023, was passed unanimously by both the houses of parliament. It came to be known as 106th constitution amendment act.¹¹

The passage of this historic bill can be seen as a transformative breakthrough in upholding women's right to political participation, making women representatives accountable to the common women and ensuring gender equality in India.

The following are some of the important clauses of Naari Shakti Vanadan Adhiniyam:

2.1. Reservation for Women in Lok Sabha

The 106th Constitutional Amendment Act provides for the reservation of seats for women in the lower house of the Indian Parliament. It inserts Article 330A to the constitution, which borrows from the provisions of Article 330, providing for the reservation of seats to SCs/STs in the Lok Sabha. Thus, one-third of the seats will be reserved for women of the SC/ST community within the SC/ST reservation quotas.¹²

Out of the total seats to be filled by direct elections to Lok Sabha, one-third will be reserved for women representatives (including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the SC/ST community).¹³

a. Reservation for women in State Legislative Assemblies

The act provides for the reservation of seats for women in the state legislative assemblies. It inserts Article 332A into the constitution, borrowing from the provisions of Article 332, which provide for the reservation of seats for SCs/STs in legislative assemblies. Therefore, one-third of the seats will be reserved for women of the SC/ST community within the SC/ST reservation quotas.¹⁴ Out of the total seats to be filled by direct elections to the Lok Sabha, one-third will be reserved for women representatives (including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the SC/ST community).¹⁵

2.3. Reservation for Women in NCT of Delhi

The act amends Art. 239 AA of the constitution, clause (2) (b), and inserts (ba), providing for the reservation of seats for women in the Legislative Assembly of the National Capital Territory of Delhi. It also inserts (bb), thus establishing one-third reservation of seats for women of the SC/ST community within the SC/ST reservation quotas. Additionally, it inserts (bc), stating that out of the total seats to be filled by direct elections in the Legislative Assembly of the National Capital Territory of Delhi, one-third shall be reserved for women, including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the Scheduled Castes

16.

2.4. Commencement of Reservation (New article - 334A)

The 106th Constitution Amendment Act introduces Article 334A (1), which states that the provisions for reserving seats for women in the Lok Sabha, the legislative assemblies of the states, and the legislative assembly of the National Capital Territory of Delhi will take effect following a delimitation exercise. This exercise is to be conducted after the relevant figures from the first census taken following the commencement of the Constitution 106th amendment Act, 2023, have been published. The reservation will last for 15 years.

Article 334A (2): However, subject to articles 239A, 330A, and 332A, the reservation shall continue until a date determined by law made by Parliament.

Article 334 A. (3) provides for rotation of Seats reserved for women after each delimitation exercise, as determined by a law made by Parliament. To give all constituencies in states or Union Territories a fair chance for ascriptive (gender-based) representation.¹⁷

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE BILL

The women's reservation bill is important in the following ways:

3.1. Addressing the Underrepresentation of Women

Women had 4.4% representation in the first Lok Sabha, which has risen to a meagre 13.6% in the 18th Lok Sabha, while in state assemblies, women have less than 10% representation.¹⁸

Reservations will help address this skewed gender representation in politics by ensuring a minimum threshold of 33 per cent seats for women legislators in parliament and state legislatures. Enabling half of our population with a significant stake in decision-making will lead to increased political candidacy of women across all representative bodies.¹⁹

a. Political Empowerment Leading to Mindset Change

Reservations will empower women by increasing their numbers in legislatures, transforming them into an effective pressure group within these bodies. Greater access to legislative power and public decision-making may inspire more women to run for office and contest elections. This, in turn, is likely to create a spillover effect in other aspects of social life, significantly influencing how women are perceived.²⁰

3.3. Women's Issues and the Benefits of Comprehensive Governance

Increasing the number of women in legislatures will create a constitutional space where women's thoughts, issues, and viewpoints are considered on a wide range of matters, including women's rights, education, health, and safety, as well as other significant issues facing the country. This, in turn, will facilitate the development of laws and policies that address discrimination and gender-based oppression. A greater presence of women Members of Parliament (MPs) in decision-making bodies will lead to improved governance and decision-making by incorporating diverse perspectives and experiences.²¹

3.4. Development of the Constituency and Increased Accountability

Research indicates that women representatives at the panchayat level are more inclined to invest in development by prioritising health, education, and access to drinking water. Furthermore, these women representatives are less likely to engage in corruption. They also play a vital role in addressing social issues such as domestic violence and child marriage. If these trends were to be replicated at the national level, it could lead to significant development within constituencies. Consequently, this could also enhance accountability among women representatives.²²

3.5. Socio-Economic Development

The political liberation of women will lead to gender-sensitive laws, access to quality healthcare, education, and skills training, as well as better economic opportunities by increasing employability and pay parity, thus transforming into social and economic progress.²³

3.6. Reducing Gender Differences

Reservations will lead to the prevalence of gender sensitive policies at national and regional levels, due to the legislative foresight of women members. This, in turn, will go a long way in reducing gender-based discrimination.

3.7. Electoral Effect

Analysis indicates that constituencies reserved for women show greater levels of female representation following the implementation of reservations. Therefore, there is a notable trend of enhanced women's representation in reserved constituencies compared to those that are unreserved.²⁴

3.8. De-Gendering of Political Parties

Establishing a 33 per cent quota for women in legislatures will encourage greater participation of women within party structures, not just as workers but also in key leadership roles. This initiative will help create a pipeline of capable women leaders for future parliamentary work. Additionally, it will challenge the stereotypes surrounding women leaders and help eliminate the inherent gender bias that exists within political parties.

4. CHALLENGES TO THE IMPLEMENTATION

The following challenges are likely to be faced in the successful implementation of women's reservation.

4.1. Patriarchy and Its Resistance to Women as Leaders

The societal stereotype that women are politically irrelevant and incapable of holding political positions may result in a widespread rejection of reservation policies. This could reduce reservations to mere tokenism resulting in symbolic gestures and empty promises. Consequently, this undermines the ability of women representatives to exercise their agency and create meaningful change.

a. Lack of Election Financing

State and parliamentary elections in India can be quite expensive. Women candidates often rely on their families for financial support. Even though they receive endorsement from their political parties, they may struggle to campaign effectively and connect with voters due to insufficient funding. This financial barrier contributes to their underrepresentation in politics.²⁵

b. Lack of Family Support

Many women with political ambitions often face discouragement from their families in pursuing their goals. In India, women are frequently expected to prioritise household responsibilities and act as primary caregivers. As a result, most women from modest backgrounds tend to consider their political aspirations only after they have fulfilled their duties as mothers.

c. The Practice of Sarpanch Pati

The practice of "sarpanch Pati" is still common in Panchayati Raj Institutions. In this scenario, women serve merely as nominal heads while their spouses or other male family members make political decisions on their behalf. This raises concerns about the effectiveness of the proposed bill. There is a possibility that this same phenomenon could also occur at the parliamentary level.²⁶

d. Violence Against Women in Politics

Women in politics experience various forms of violence, including character assassination, physical aggression during election campaigns, and even sexual assault. Research indicates that this violence is a reflection of gender discrimination fostered by the patriarchal society in India. Such violence discourages women from pursuing their political aspirations.²⁷

e. Delay in Implementation

The reservation of seats for women will take place after the delimitation exercise is completed, and the data from the first census conducted under the 128th Constitutional Amendment Act of 2023 will be available. This process will require considerable time, which presents a significant challenge for its implementation due to potential delays.²⁸

4.7. Omission of Reservation for OBC Women

The Women's Reservation Bill does not address the issue of OBC (Other Backwards Classes) reservations in the legislature. The Mandal Commission's report from 1980 indicated that over 52% of Indian women belong to the OBC category. As a result, their representation will likely increase, making them a significant segment of the women's vote bank. This growth underscores the need for fair representation of OBC women in Parliament.²⁹

5. CONCLUSION

The Women's Reservation Act of 2023 is a monumental stride toward elevating the political representation of women in India, reserving one-third of seats in both the Lok Sabha and state assemblies. This progressive act is not just a legislative change; it is a powerful statement in our ongoing fight against gender inequality. By ensuring that women have a dedicated voice in our legislatures, we are not only rectifying historical injustices but also enriching our democratic framework with diverse perspectives and experiences.

Now, the urgent task before us is to implement this Act swiftly and efficiently, eliminating unnecessary delays that could hinder its impact. We must foster a political landscape in which women can flourish as leaders and decision-makers on equal footing with their male counterparts. However, it is crucial to approach the concept of reservations with a discerning eye; they should be viewed as short-term strategies that pave the way for a more equitable environment, empowering women to make meaningful contributions to policy-making.

As we welcome more women into our political sphere, we will inevitably shine a spotlight on issues that resonate with women and seek solutions tailored to their unique challenges. This shift could usher in fresh, innovative perspectives on the myriad issues facing our nation, leading to transformative, gender-sensitive solutions. Moreover, increased women's representation is not just about the present; it will lay the groundwork for a future generation of effective and dynamic leaders, bridging the gender divide and enriching our society as a whole.

REFERENCES

1. Nagar, K., & Dixit, A. (2023) a. Enhancing Democratic Representation: A Comprehensive Analysis of Women's Reservation Policies. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, Volume 5, Issue 6.
2. Desai, S., & Temsah, G. (2014). Women's Political Representation in India: Understanding the Role of Party Politics. *India Review*, 13(3), 207–230.
3. Jan, Saima. (2024) a. Women's Reservation in India: A Critical Study of The Legislation, Developments and Challenges. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, Volume 12, Issue 2, d45-d51.
4. Raju, M Bhaskara. (2024). The women reservation act, 2023: What, why, and how an imperative step towards gender equality. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Volume 11, Issue 11, Page No. 38-41.
5. Jan, Saima. (2024) b. Women's Reservation in India: A Critical Study of the Legislation, Developments and Challenges. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, Volume 12, Issue 2, d45-d51.
6. Nagar, K., & Dixit, A. (2023) b. Enhancing Democratic Representation: A Comprehensive Analysis of Women's Reservation Policies. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, Volume 5, Issue 6.

7. Kaur, Navneet. (2025) a. Empowering representation: A critical analysis of the women's reservation bill 2023. *Int. J. Arts Humanit. Social Stud.*;7(1):540-543. DOI: 10.33545/26648652.2025.v7.i1g.226
8. https://prsindia.org/files/bills_acts/bills_parliament/2008/bill184_20080923184_National_policy_for_empowerment_of_women.pdf
9. <https://constitutionnet.org/news/almost-thirty-years-reach-one-third-will-indias-constitutional-amendment-enhance-womens>
10. <https://prsindia.org/billtrack/prs-products/prs-bill-summary-4251>
11. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/womens-reservation-bill-gets-presidents-assent/article67361561.ece>
12. Devi, Pallavi. (2023) a. An Analysis of The Nari Shakti Vandan Adhiniyam Bill 2023: Paving the Way for Women's Empowerment in Legislation. *Mizoram University Journal Of Humanities & Social Sciences*, Vol.IX, Issue 2, 163-172.
13. <https://egazette.gov.in/WriteReadData/2023/249053.pdf>
14. Devi, Pallavi. (2023) b. An Analysis of The Nari Shakti Vandan Adhiniyam Bill 2023: Paving the Way for Women's Empowerment in Legislation. *Mizoram University Journal Of Humanities & Social Sciences*, Vol.IX, Issue 2, 163-172.
15. <https://egazette.gov.in/WriteReadData/2023/249053.pdf> a
16. Ibid.
17. Ibid.
18. <https://vajiramandravi.com/upsc-exam/women-reservation-bill/>
19. Kaur, Navneet. (2025) b. Empowering representation: A critical analysis of the women's reservation bill 2023. *Int. J. Arts Humanit. Social Stud.*;7(1):540-543. DOI: 10.33545/26648652.2025.v7.i1g.226
20. <https://www.ideasforindia.in/topics/social-identity/india-s-women-s-reservation-act-a-big-win-for-governance-and-beyond.html>
21. Kaur, Navneet. (2025) c. Empowering representation: A critical analysis of the women's reservation bill 2023. *Int. J. Arts Humanit. Social Stud.*;7(1):540-543. DOI: 10.33545/26648652.2025.v7.i1g.226
22. <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/lessons-from-30-years-of-women-s-reservation-in-panchayats>
23. Suriyapriya, E. (2024) Women Reservation Bill 2023: An Analytical Study. *JETIR*, Volume 11, Issue 1, c370-c377.

24. Jan, Saima. (2024) c. Women's Reservation in India: A Critical Study of The Legislation, Developments and Challenges. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Volume 12, Issue 2, d45-d51.
25. Kaur, Navneet. (2025) d. Empowering representation: A critical analysis of the women's reservation bill 2023. Int. J. Arts Humanit. Social Stud.;7(1):540-543. DOI: 10.33545/26648652.2025.v7.i1g.226
26. Kumar N. The untold story of Haryana's women sarpanches. The Times of India [Internet]. Available from: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/theuntold-story-of-haryanas-women-sarpanches-womenremain-in-kitchens-men-take-care-of-officialwork/articleshow/xyz>
27. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2014/6/violence-against-women-in-politics>
28. Kaur, Navneet. (2025) e. Empowering representation: A critical analysis of the women's reservation bill 2023. Int. J. Arts Humanit. Social Stud.;7(1):540-543. DOI: 10.33545/26648652.2025.v7.i1g.226
29. Nithish Kumar N.P., Gokul B., Arunkumar N. and Vishal Anand. (2023). Analyzing the Challenges of Women Reservation.6 (6) IJLMH Page1104-1115, DOI: <https://doij.org/10.1000/IJLMH.116107>

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